

Nutraceuticals: Let Food Be the Medicine

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Introduction

The concept of nutraceuticals is not entirely new, although it has evolved considerably over the years. Addition of iodine to the salt, in the early 1900s, to prevent goitre represents one of the first attempts at creating nutraceuticals. The nutraceutical revolution began in the early 1980s, a continuous stream of published clinical studies followed, defining the potential benefits of a growing range of products on a rapidly expanding array of specific disease processes. Even several centuries ago; greek physician Hippocrates, also known as father of Medicine said that “Let Food be Your Medicine”.

The term nutraceutical was coined from “nutrition” and “pharmaceutical” in 1989 by Stephen DeFelice and he proceeded to define nutraceutical as, “a food (or part of a food) that provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and or treatment of a disease”

In year 1996, North American Veterinary Nutraceutical Council defined Veterinary nutraceuticals as “a [non-drug] substance which is produced in a purified or extracted form and administered orally to a patient to provide agents required for normal body structure and function and administered with the intent of improving the health and well-being of animals.” While American Veterinary Medical Association in 1999 defined the veterinary nutraceuticals as “those micronutrients, macronutrients and other nutritional supplements which could be used as therapeutic agents”. The United States National Research Council (NRC) prefers the term Animal Dietary supplement rather than nutraceuticals.

Idiosyncrasy Of Nutraceuticals

Nutraceuticals could be differentiated from the Pharmaceutical on the basis of following points.

Nutraceuticals	Pharmaceuticals
These compounds have low potency.	These compounds have high potency.
These interacts with the target molecule weakly.	These interacts with the target molecule strongly.
These are mainly used for prevention or inhibition of diseases.	These are used for treatment of diseases.
For the beneficial effect, these need to be applied or consumed for a long time.	These could produce beneficial effect within the short-term application.
These substances intervene with several physiological process to produce their effect.	These compounds more specifically intervene with the physiological mechanism.

Classification Of Nutraceuticals

Veterinary nutraceuticals could be classified in a variety of manner. But the most convenient way of classification are -

- A. On the basis of chemical nature
- B. On the basis of food availability
- C. On the basis of mechanism of action or therapeutic activity.

A. Based on Chemical Nature:

i. Fatty acids –

☐ Conjugated linoleic acids (CLA) –

- **Source** : Ruminants dairy Products (Milk Fat)
- **Benefits** : Anti-carcinogenic activity, Anti-obesity activity, Anti-atherogenic activity, Anti-diabetic activity

☐ Omega -3 Fatty acids –

- **Source** : Fish oils, berseem & maize fodder, linseed oil, soybean oil, algae, canola etc.
- **Benefits** : Reduce cardio-vascular diseases & improve mental and visual function, Prevention of diabetes, cancer & rheumatoid arthritis

ii. Polyphenols –

☐ Anthocyanidine, Catechins, Flavones, Flavonone –

- **Source** : Fruits, vegetables, soybean, citrus fruits, tea, babul pods, mustard cake, rape seed, salseed
- **Benefits** : Neutralizes free radicals, Reduce risk of cancer
- Proanthocyanidine –
- **Source** : Cocoa, chocolate, tea, rape seed
- **Benefits** : Reduce cardio-vascular diseases

- iii. **Saponins** –
 - **Source** : Soybeans, GNC, lucerne, chick pea
 - **Benefits** : Lower blood cholesterol, Anti-cancer
- iv. **Probiotics / Prebiotics / Synbiotics** –
 - ☐ Lactobacilli –
 - **Source** : Dahi, yoghurt
 - **Benefits** : Improves gastro-intestinal health
 - ☐ Fructo-oligosaccharide –
 - **Source** : Whole grains, yeast
 - **Benefits** : improves GI health
- v. **Phytoestrogen** –
 - ☐ Diadzein, Zenistein –
 - **Source** : Soybean, flaxseed, lentil seed, maize, berseem, lucerne, subabul fodder
 - **Benefits** : Improves reproductive performance, meat quality and bone health
 - ☐ Lignans–
 - **Source** : Flax, rye and vegetables
 - **Benefits** : Reduce cancer and heart diseases
- vi. **Caroteinoids** –
 - ☐ β -carotene–
 - **Source** : Berseem, lucerne, oat & maize fodder, carrots, vegetabels, fruits
 - **Benefits** : Neutralizes free radicals and improves eye vision
 - ☐ Zeoxanthine –
 - **Source** : Eggs, citrus, corn
 - **Benefits** : Healthy vision
 - ☐ Lycopenes–
 - **Source** : Tomatoes
 - **Benefits** : Reduce the risk of benign prostatic cancer in dogs
- vii. **Dietary fiber** – Insoluble fibre and beta-glucan are present in wheat bran and oats. This prevents the incidence of cardiovascular diseases and cancer.
- viii. **Fat Soluble Vitamins** –
 - ☐ Vitamin- A (Retinol) –
 - **Source** : Egg, liver, cheese, butter, milk, coloured vegetables & fruits
 - **Benefits** : Acts as antioxidant, Essential for growth and development, Maintains healthy vision, skin and mucous membranes, may also aid in the prevention and treatment of certain cancers and in the treatment of certain skin disorders.
 - ☐ Vitamin- D (Calciferol) –
 - **Source** : Synthesized in the body by sunlight; Egg yolk , liver, fatty fish, fortified milk
 - **Benefits** : Essential for the formation of bones and teeth, helps the body to absorb and use calcium

- ❑ Vitamin- E (Tocoferol) –
 - **Source** : Polyunsaturated plant oils, fish oils, green leafy vegetable (GLV), liver, egg yolk
 - **Benefits** : Antioxidant, helps to form blood cells, also boost the immune system
- ❑ Vitamin- K (Phylloquinone) –
 - **Source** : Bacterial synthesis in gut, green leafy vegetable, milk
 - **Benefits** : Essential for blood clotting
- ix. **Water Soluble Vitamins** –
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₁ (Thiamine) –
 - **Source** : Pork products, cereals, legumes
 - **Benefits** : Helps in carbohydrate metabolism, also essential for neurological function
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₂ (Riboflavin) –
 - **Source** : Milk, yoghurt, GLV (Spinach), cheese
 - **Benefits** : Energy metabolism, maintain healthy eye, skin and nerve function
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₃ (Niacin) –
 - **Source** : Milk, eggs, meat, fish, all protein containing foods
 - **Benefits** : Energy metabolism, brain function
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₅ (Pantothenic Acid) –
 - **Source** : widespread in foods
 - **Benefits** : Helps to produce essential proteins, Aids in synthesis of cholesterol, steroids, and fatty acids, Crucial for intraneuronal synthesis of acetylcholine
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₆ (Pyridoxine) –
 - **Source** : widespread in foods
 - **Benefits** : Helps to produce essential proteins
 - ❑ Vitamin – B₁₂ (Cyanocobalamin) –
 - **Source** : Animal Products like meat, fish, poultry, milk, cheese, eggs
 - **Benefits** : Helps in producing genetic material, Formation of RBC, Maintenance of CNS, Synthesis of amino acids, Involved in metabolism of protein, fat and carbohydrate
 - ❑ Vitamin – C (Ascorbic Acid) –
 - **Source** : Citrus fruits, dark green vegetables, tomatoes, potatoes, mango
 - **Benefits** : Acts as antioxidant, Necessary for healthy bones, gums, teeth and skin, Helps in wound healing
 - ❑ Folic Acid –
 - **Source** : Green leafy vegetables, legumes, liver, sunflower seed
 - **Benefits** : Helps in RBC formation, formation of genetic material of cell

x. **Minerals –**

- **Source :** Various feed and fodder, commercially prepared mineral mixtures .

S.No.	Minerals	Functions
1.	Calcium (Ca)	Essential for bone growth and teeth
2.	Iron (Fe)	Energy production
3.	Magnesium (Mg)	For healthy muscle and nerve formation
4.	Phosphorous (P)	Energy production, bone strength and important for production of energy
5.	Cobalt (Co)	Component of vitamin B-12 & its coenzymes
6.	Iodine (I)	Proper function of thyroid gland
7.	Chromium (Cr)	Convert carbohydrates and fat into energy with the help of insulin , also potentiate insulin activity
8.	Selenium (Se)	Antioxidant and part of GSH (Glutathione) enzyme
9.	Zinc (Zn)	Help in wound healing and Neonates body organ formation and cell reproduction

B. Based on Food Availability:

- **Traditional Nutraceuticals –**

a. Chemical Constituents:

- **Nutrients** – Such as vitamins, amino acids with nutritional functions such as Taurine etc.
- **Herbs** – Herbs or botanical products as concentrates and extracts confers beneficial properties to the animals.

Name of Herbs	Therapeutic Property
Aloe-vera	Anti-inflammatory and help in wound healing
Ginger	Carminative, antiemetic and also cure dizziness
Ginseng	Antioxidant and enhance humoral and cell mediated immunity
Garlic	Anti bacterial and anti-inflammatory effects
Asafoetida	Stimulant, carminative, expectorant
Bael	Digestive appetizer, treatment of diarrhea and dysentery
Brahmi	Nervine tonic, spasmolytic, anti-anxiety

Amla	Vitamin C rich, balance neuroendocrine system, fight against lungs problems
Onion	Hypo- glyceemic activity and anti-atherosclerosis
Turmeric	Anti-inflammatory, pain relief, improving liver function, reduces risk of cancer, improve digestion
Senna	Purgatives
Valeriana	Tranquillizer, migraine, intestinal cramps, bronchial spasm
Golden seal (Dried root of <i>Hydrastis canadensis</i>)	Antimicrobial, astringent, antihemorrhagic, treatment of mucosal inflammation

- **Phytochemicals** – Phytochemicals could provide health benefits such as these can acts as substrate for biochemical reactions, as cofactors & inhibitors of enzymatic reactions, as absorbents that bind to & eliminate undesirable constituent in the intestine and also scavenges of reactive or toxic chemicals, can enhance the absorption and stability of essential nutrients etc.

Few Examples of Phytochemicals are –

- **Tocotrienols & tocopherols** → Suppressed the growth of diverse tumors cell lines via initiation of apoptosis and concomitant arrest of cells in the G₁ phase of the cell cycle
- **Phytosterols** (present in various plants) → Exhibit anti-inflammatory, anti-neoplastic, anti-pyretic & immune- modulating activity, decrease cholesterol,
- **Phenolic constituents** (present in various plants, wholegrain) → Antioxidants, lowers the risk of CVD, diabetes, hypertension etc.,
- **Limonoids** (present in citrus fruits) → Inhibiting phase-I enzymes & inducing phase-II detoxification enzymes in liver, provide protection to lung tissue.

- b. **Probiotics Microorganisms / Direct-Fed Microbials (DFM):** Probiotics are live culture of nonpathogenic microbes promoting the gut health by competitive exclusion of harmful bacteria improving intestinal microbial balance. **OR** “A live microbial feed supplement which beneficially affects the host animal by improving its intestinal balance”.

These function as growth and health stimulators and used extensively in animal feeding, especially in pig and poultry production. These transforms the toxic flora of intestine into a host-friendly colony of lactobacilli spp.

- c. **Nutraceutical Enzymes:** Such as Hemicellulase enzyme (Obtained from mushrooms and microbes), Pancreo-lipase enzymes (from Pancreatic Juice) etc.

- **Non-Traditional Nutraceuticals –**

These are of 2 types i.e.

- 1. Fortified Nutraceuticals:** These are either obtained from agricultural breeding or by addition of any exogenous nutrients.

2. Recombinant Nutraceuticals: Such nutraceuticals are result of any biotechnological or genetic engineering process.

C. Based on Therapeutic Activity or Property:

- ❑ **Nutraceuticals for Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) –**
 - **Anti-oxidants, Dietary fibres, Omega-3 poly unsaturated fatty acids, Vitamins, minerals** for prevention and treatment of CVD
 - **Polyphenols** prevent and control arterial diseases
 - **Flavonoids** (in onion, vegetables, grapes, apples, and cherries) block the ACE and strengthen the tiny capillaries that carry oxygen and essential nutrients to all cells.
- ❑ **Nutraceuticals for Cancer –**
 - **Flavonoids** which block the enzymes that produce estrogen reduce of estrogen-induced cancers.
 - **Saponins** (found in peas, soybeans, some herbs, spinach, tomatoes, potatoes, alfalfa and clover) contain antitumor and anti- mutagenic activities.
 - To prevent prostate cancer a broad range of **phyto-pharmaceuticals** with a claimed hormonal activity, called “phyto-estrogens” is recommended
 - **Curcumin** (di-feruloylmethane) which is a polyphenol of turmeric possesses anticarcinogenic, antioxidative and anti-inflammatory properties.
 - **Top of Beet roots, cucumber fruits, spinach leaves, and turmeric rhizomes**, were reported to possess anti tumor activity
 - **Lycopene** concentrates in the skin, testes, adrenal and prostate where it protects against cancer
- ❑ **Nutraceuticals for Obesity –**
 - **Herbal stimulants**, such as ephedrine, caffeine, chitosan etc. help in body weight loss.
 - **Buckwheat seed proteins** acting similar to natural fibers present in food
 - **5-hydroxytryptophan** and **green tea extract** may promote weight loss, while the former decreases appetite, the later increases the energy expenditure
 - A **blend of glucomannan, chitosan, fenugreek, G sylvestre, and vitamin C** in the dietary supplement significantly reduced body weight
 - Conjugated linoleic acid (**CLA**), **Momordica charantia** (possesses potential anti obese properties)
- ❑ **Nutraceuticals for Diabetes Mellitus –**
 - **Ethyl esters** of n-3 fatty acids
 - **Docosahexaenoic acid** modulates insulin resistance and is also vital for neuro-visual development
 - **Lipoic acid**, an antioxidant, for treatment of diabetic neuropathy
 - **Dietary fibres from psyllium** have been used for glucose control in diabetic animals and to reduce lipid levels in hyper-lipidemia.
- ❑ **Nutraceuticals for Osteo-arthritis –**
 - **Glucosamine** and **chondroitin sulphate** alleviates the symptoms of osteo-arthritis.
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Conclusion

- Nutraceuticals may range from isolated nutrients, dietary supplements and diets to genetically engineered designer food, herbal products and processed foods. The nutraceutical has variety of therapeutic actions, which protect the animal's body over the various pathological conditions.
- Nutraceutical in chronic disorders play key role such in Diabetes mellitus, Cancer, Obesity, Osteoarthritis and also in Neuro-degenerative disorders.
- Herbal nutraceutical is a powerful instrument in maintaining health and to act against nutritionally induced acute and chronic diseases, thereby promoting optimal health, longevity, and quality of life.
- Besides their beneficial effects, there are some limitations for using nutraceuticals like Poor bioavailability is the major constraint for their uses; as nutraceuticals get eliminated from the body very easily and fail to provide significant medicinal benefit. Beyond their effective doses, nutraceuticals may pose toxicity.
- So Further research is needed to not only identify new or improved possibilities of nutraceuticals but also need to understand that how combinations of these nutraceuticals can be used to improve the efficiency of animal's performance.

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